

Increasing the Role of the Centre of Peace, Conflict, and Democracy (CPCD) Unhas to Prevent Continued Social Conflict

Dwia Aries Tina Pulubuhu¹, Rahmatia², Sherry Adelia³, Siti Fatimah⁴, Amril Hans⁵, Senwiati⁶

¹Sociology Department, Social and Political Sciences Faculty, Hasanuddin University, Makassar, South Sulawesi, Indonesia

²Economic Department, Economic and Business Faculty, Hasanuddin University, Makassar, South Sulawesi, Indonesia

³Economic Department, Economic and Business Faculty, Muhammadiyah University, Makassar, South Sulawesi, Indonesia

⁴Government Department, Social and Political Sciences Faculty, Yapis University, Papua, Jayapura, Indonesia

⁵Public Administration Department, Social and Political Sciences Faculty, Hasanuddin University, Makassar, South Sulawesi, Indonesia

⁶International Relations Department, Social and Political Sciences Faculty, Hasanuddin University, Makassar, South Sulawesi, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This service activity aims to enhance the impact of the Center of Peace, Conflict, and Democracy (CPCD) in the Wajo District by raising participants' comprehension of conflict resolution and honing their negotiation abilities. The CPCD team has determined that conflicts between the residents of Wajo and PT Perkebunan Nusantara (PTPN) stem from disputes over land use rights (HGU). The research center at Hasanuddin University assisted in conflict areas, specifically in South Sulawesi and eastern Indonesia. Furthermore, CPCD delivered messages in training to identify possible opportunities for conflict resolution. To evaluate the outcomes of the training, the securitization approach was utilized, which focuses on the actions taken by actors such as local government officials, for example regents, sub-district heads, and village heads. The training results show that their level of understanding is increasing, and the CPCD's approach is novel in this region.

KEYWORDS: CPCD, Securitization, Conflicts, Government, Wajo District.

I. INTRODUCTION

Conflict is a natural occurrence in society and can be challenging to resolve due to the complex nature of social interactions and differences. An example of conflict is land disputes, which are common in agrarian societies such as Indonesia (Zakie, 2016), and the country's natural conditions are relevant to the presence. Conflicts occur when people think their land rights have been infringed or the land is under threat of being taken by the government or company. Indigenous communities often view themselves as having inherited land ownership rights based on traditional customs, resulting in areas considered customary land or forest (Kamaruddin, Najamuddin and Patahuddin, 2018). Consequently, this develops into a potential conflict caused by different views on the interests of certain land ownership. A land dispute is a struggle over ownership rights (Zakie, 2016) between multiple parties, with conflicting claims leading to the friction of interests and potentially escalating into larger disputes. These disputes, known as agrarian conflicts, have been ongoing in Indonesia for a long time without resolution. They generally involve communities, companies, or corporations that relate to land disputes and inadequate natural resource management (Fahrimal and Safpuriyadi, 2018). Therefore, the conflicts could be minimized through the optimal use of natural resources, specifically with clear directions regarding land status.

Land is a major resource used as a source of production, attracting interest from various parties (Zakie, 2016). These parties may use various methods to utilize the land for profitable productivity, making it a highly sought-after resource. As a result, disputes and conflicts over land become more prevalent. This activity aimed to increase the role of the Centre of Peace, Conflict, and Democracy (CPCD), a research centre under Hasanuddin University. The CPCD team identified land disputes between the people of Wajo and PT Perkebunan Nusantara (PTPN) as the cause of conflict and assisted in resolving the issues in South Sulawesi and eastern Indonesia. The research center prepares peacebuilders and makers among the younger generation to become skilled negotiators and consultants for politics and democracy. It is hoped that through this activity, the community will better understand appropriate conflict resolution methods to be applied in their area.

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II. METHOD

The method used in this community service activity is the training held for three days in the city of Sengkang, Wajo Regency, in August 2022 to May 2023. CPCD presented material on understanding conflict resolution and the importance of this approach. On the first day, issues related to the social conflict were explored with the 20 training participants. Furthermore, the causes of the conflict were identified, with the actors involved in the conflict before the capabilities of NGOs and local governments in resolving conflicts. On the second day, NGOs, village heads, sub-district heads, stakeholders, and journalists were invited to attend the training with 50 people. On the third day, NGOs were called to share their activities in resolving conflicts in the Wajo district, totaling 34 people in the last five years. In addition to conducting training, interviews were conducted with participants to obtain updated conditions regarding the social conflict situation in the Wajo district. The following are the methods of activity conducted:

F.1. Training Activities

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

On the first day of the service activity, the CPCD team provided training on conflict and conflict management, highlighting how government policies often lead to agrarian conflicts (Hak, Nonci and Budiarto, 2019). This issue should be known to ensure that the government, community, and company collaborate in providing mutual benefits and not conflicts due to land issues. Additionally, the team discussed how agrarian conflicts are further complicated by overlapping government policies (Fahrimal and Safpuriyadi, 2018), which prolongs the conflicts due to a lack of clarity in land processing and ownership.

On the first day, the CPCD team also explained about agrarian conflicts between corporations and the community showing considerable tension in society in the agrarian sector. This was evidenced by various riots (Zakie, 2016) caused by the rejection of land. This condition should be understood to find a solution that benefits both parties. Unfortunately, companies often hold more power in the arrangement and utilization of agrarian resources based on economic interests (Kamaruddin, Najamuddin, and Patahuddin, 2018), which can lead to an imbalance of power between the company and the community (Kamaruddin, Najamuddin, and Patahuddin, 2018). This results in many individuals feeling oppressed and fighting for their rights. Even though previous literature has focused on the causes of conflicts, the resolution has not been explored through the role of research centers. On the first day of training, the participants were very engaged in listening to the CPCD team's explanations and learned about the main conflict issues in the Wajo district. On the second day, the CPCD team discussed various agrarian conflicts in Indonesia involving communities and companies, such as those between communities and PTPN. Disputes involving PTPN occurred in almost all regions in South Sulawesi (Arbani, 2020), including Wajo District. They have been ongoing for a long time without resolution and have become a popular topic of discussion (Hamid, Tina, and Cangara, 2015). Armayani, a regional secretary of Wajo District, stated that the conflicts could be protracted and difficult to resolve for both parties (interview, Wajo District, August 3, 2022).

On the second day of the training, the secretary of the Development Planning Agency, Regional Research, and Development of the Wajo District, Mrs. Susiawati, stated that the conflicts were rooted in the plantation development conducted by PTPN XIV. In this case, PTPN XIV aimed to manufacture industrial raw materials but now produces palm oil (interview, Wajo district, August 3, 2022). This has resulted in large-scale land concentration by the company for its plantation use, and the first company in Keera-Wajo, PT Bina Mulya Ternak, which was originally a livestock company, has now converted to an oil palm plantation. The

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condition caused public anxiety about continuous evictions, triggering anger and protests by the people feeling disadvantaged and losing land for production and a source of livelihood due to the conversion. Consequently, the community became increasingly aware of demanding their rights to land controlled by PTPN. Initially, they worked as farmers, but the broken promises of land contracts escalated the conflicts (Hamid, Tina, and Cangara, 2015). Tajuddin Sunusi, chairman of the NGO LPKPK, stated that this condition made people more aggressive in protesting land ownership (interview, Wajo district, August 3, 2022).

The CPCD team explained further about the main conflicts between PTPN and the people of South Sulawesi related to the government granting permits to PTPN XIV through land use rights HGU to manage 66,484.75 Ha. The conflicts were then caused by the issue of HGU, which became a separate polemic. Plantation HGU ensures that state land is of good use as a well-managed sector of state income. However, for the HGU, conflicts are escalating due to the expiration of PTPN, specifically as the government has failed to take firm action (Arbani, 2020). According to Nasir Rahim, the head of the NGO Lidik Pro, the people of Wajo demand that PTPN vacate the land following the absence of the right to conduct business activities in the area (interview, Wajo district, August 3, 2022).

The CPCD team further explained that land management practices carried out by PTPN without clear HGU had become a major problem in this conflict. A misunderstanding exists between the community and the company regarding land management, resulting in conflicts and riots. Residents believe that the expiration of the HGU would leave PTPN with no rights over the land, allowing the people to carry out their activities. However, PTPN claimed ownership of the land because it was extending the HGU (Arbani, 2020). Andi Muspida, the head of the SDN NGO, stated that the difference in perceptions triggered the ongoing conflicts because the two parties were contradictory and noncompromising (interview, Wajo district, August 3, 2022).

The CPCD team also showed the trainees how to land monopolies, or tenure practices create problems regarding ownership and social inequality caused by economic factors (Hamid, Tina, and Cangara, 2015). In Wajo District, land tenure by PTPN XIV in the Sakkoli Wajo unit has an HGU area of around 4,583 hectares (Arbani, 2020). This extensive area could make the community demand using the land for their benefit. Moreover, various demands and agreements between residents and companies whose fulfillment is unclear have made conflicts unavoidable. The farming community needs land to meet their daily needs because they are forced to rely on uncertain labor and income working on other farms. This has driven the farming labor class to fight for their rights to the land through various efforts, such as forming the United People's Forum (FRB) organization for the Wajo people. The community also held demonstrations to collect promises made by the government to release land for the benefit of residents (Nurdin, 2014). The resulting challenge was many land needs by the community and company (Zakie, 2016). Andi Pallawarukan, a government figure and head of the Wajo District BAPPELITBANGDA, stated that this condition promotes a greater desire for land tenure due to its great productivity (interview, Wajo district, August 3, 2022).

F.2. Training Activities

Conflicts in Wajo, as illustrated by Arbani (2020), demonstrate the complex agrarian conditions in South Sulawesi. According to Inoi Nur, a government figure and head of Kesbangpol (National and Political Unity), land ownership is a major challenge for economic prosperity in the region. Companies often manage land for economic purposes, but the local community experiences losses as they cannot utilize it to meet their daily needs. As a result, real conflicts arise due to the differences in interests between the two parties, further exacerbated by a lack of regulations and overlapping land ownership claims. Despite these ongoing conflicts, there have been few efforts from various parties to address and resolve them. Therefore, the government must take a

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proactive role in mediating these issues, as both the community and companies are affected and depend on the land for their livelihoods (interview, Wajo district, August 3, 2022).

According to Kamaruddin, Najamuddin, and Patahuddin (2018), these agrarian conflicts can be seen as a learning opportunity for improving land use. Conflicts can be minimized when land is used properly, all parties are open to finding mutually beneficial solutions, and collaboration is needed to achieve goals without harming the other party. The ongoing conflicts between PTPN and the Wajo community have been a long-standing issue, making it imperative that both sides take a positive step toward reducing tensions. Therefore, they should work together to find options for preventing future disputes over land ownership. Gradual collaboration in land management can be a step toward resolving these conflicts.

At the close of day three, it was illustrated that there is a need for participatory land mapping efforts by the government for indigenous peoples to minimize conflicts over land ownership (Muh. Kamin, Amal, and Khandiq, 2018). The government should also formulate relevant policies related to land ownership. This would minimize agrarian conflicts by preventing a double perception of land ownership and use by the community, company, or corporation. Consequently, it would be a new beginning for economic prosperity, and people no longer worried about agrarian conflicts. The interview and training results showed that CPCD offered to assist in problem-solving. The solution was based on the root causes of the problems, the actors involved, and the possibility of mediation. Based on field data, the sources of conflicts were categorized as follows: there is a struggle for land, one party feels unfairly treated, and the actors involved have different perceptions, and it is difficult to find agreement.

After participating in this training activity, the securitization theory analyzed this service activity, a compromise between the orthodox realist understanding of security that focuses on war and the postmodernist conception. Securitization refers to making an issue an extraordinary existential threat demanding the suspension of normal political functions. The theory of securitizing speech act could also be used to analyze the construction of security issues as an existential threat. This speech act becomes a fundamental part of creating a broader discourse that defines certain social realities (Odolezyk, 2020). Furthermore, the use of securitization theory in the speech act section is very suitable for analyzing the cases in Wajo by increasing the role of the research centre. It is developed by orthodox realists focusing mainly on post-modernization security concepts of military and other issues involving actors in a conflict.

The important aspect of the securitization process is that the actor should have great power to build social and political threats (Odolezyk, 2020). In the Wajo case, the securitization theory relates to the government's role as the highest authority or respected actor. Zainuddin, chairman of the NGO JPKP Nasional, stated that the Wajo regent often delivered speeches urging the actors in the conflicts to be patient and find solutions to prevent casualties (interview, Wajo district, August 8, 2022). Several Copenhagen school scientists who first introduced the securitization concept, stating that securitizing actors built security problems through speech act (Melati, 2020). This statement mean that securitization is based on the Copenhagen School school of thought, where a problem precedes a process before becoming a national security issue. In this case, the actors perform speech acts to build an issue considered a threat. CPCD always conveys messages in workshop activities to identify possible opportunities for conflict resolution in the Wajo District. The speech act is performed only by those with the power to reduce threats. In this case, CPCD has power because it has been approved by the regents to resolve the problems.

Securitization comprises practices, contexts, and power relations that build threats through an intersubjective process. According to McDonald, the process has four variables, including (1) actors or agents that launch a securitization policy, (2) a destructive threat, (3) objects protected from the securitization process, and (4) actors that should be convinced to accept securitized issues as threats (Melati, 2020). The conflicts in Wajo showed that the district head issued a policy, and the destructive threat was the dominance of an actor in the land conflict. The domination was due to the difficulty of reaching a win-win solution agreement, causing rifts within community groups. Furthermore, the referent object protected from the securitization process was the struggle for land between the company and the surrounding community.

The concept of securitization starts with framing by speech acts from the government or executive associated with threats. The securitizers then politicize this perception as an urgent problem and threaten national security (Melati, 2020). Securitization could be described through the processes carried out by the government or the executive as actors in making an issue be considered important for securitization. In the conflicts in Wajo, the actors are the regents' government, the Ministry of State-Owned Enterprises, the Ministry of Finance, and the Ministry of Agrarian Affairs. These ministries should participate in resolving agrarian conflicts. The next process is the ministry performing speech acts to justify security issues. The interviews found that NGOs and CPCD have conducted many speech act activities in collaboration with government actors to prevent farmer criminalization.

Securitization actors further politicize the issue as an urgent threat to the country's national security. Wahyuddin Sultana, chairman of the NGO Kobar Indonesia, stated that the government's attention is still suboptimal because the company refused to release land assets demanded by the evicted community (interview, Wajo district, August 9, 2022). However, it is important to assess whether securitization can be achieved when the actors convince the audience to believe an issue is a security threat. The process is successful when the audience agrees that the issue is a threat. Besse Sunarti, the secretary of a friendly NGO, stated that

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the government always asked to help resolve agrarian conflicts in Wajo (interview, Wajo district, August 9, 2022). The involvement of NGOs and CPCD is a big effort from the government and other actors in solving the agrarian conflicts. The actors agree that land conflicts could cause security threats due to protests by people who feeling they have no rights over land. In the media process, CPCD asked the Wajo District government to grant the community land certificates in conflict-ridden villages. NGOs made this request because the National Land Agency (BPN) only registers locations in non-conflicts areas. Therefore, the community could not present their land titles when asked by the court.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The activities of the CPCD team showed that the Wajo District government, NGOs, and other training participants had carried out securitization in reconstructing the general public's understanding of land or agrarian conflicts. The actors involved have the power to build community understanding regarding a security threat to ensure patience in overcoming the conflict. The results of this training indicate an increase in the participants' understanding of conflict resolution. Training participants also gain negotiation, mediation, and decision-making skills appropriate for dealing with conflict.

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